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Title:
Implementation of a Vortex Cylinder Model to the ENERCON Blade Element Momentum method

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Abstract

This project aims to implement a vortex cylinder (VC) model within the in-house EN-ERCON Blade Element momentum method to form the BEM-VC. It then compares aero-dynamic load and power simulated results from the BEM and BEM-VC with CFD and field measurement data. The planar assumption of the BEM was relaxed by taking into account the radially varying flap-wise deflection along the blade span. Aerodynamic load and power simulations were conducted under uniform and non-uniform inflow conditions using the BEM and BEM-VC models on four different ENERCON turbine models with unique blade and rotor configurations and compared with CFD and field measurement data. This work examines the influence of the vortex cylinder model on turbine load and power predictions for a rotor undergoing elastic deformation. Therefore, addressing limitations from prior investigations of the vortex cylinder model, which inadequately captures the effects of an elastically deformed blade on aerodynamic load and power performance. The BEM-VC shows a better prediction of load and power than the BEM when compared to CFD and field measurement data, especially for the out-of-plane shape rotor configuration as well as under uniform and non-uniform inflow conditions. The tip loss correction model implemented in the in-house BEM is also investigated. A large deviation of absolute load prediction for the straight blade configuration was identified when compared with CFD was identified and this is due to the different blade element discretization used in the CFD and generic turbine models. The load predicted by the BEM and BEM-VC models for the straight blade configuration was identical. For the dihedral blade configuration, the BEM-VC is predicted to double the loads compared to the BEM as in the straight blade test case. Furthermore, the BEM-VC predicts a lesser load for the elastically deformed blade compared to the dihedral blade configuration due to lesser fluid-to-structure interaction. The BEM-VC model predicted an insignificant impact of rotor tilting on the predicted loads for all test cases, and this is because during tilting the entire rotor plane is affected, while the BEM-VC method primarily accounts for changes in blade geometry, such as dihedral and cone angle. Finally, under non-uniform inflow conditions such as shear and veer, the BEM-VC performs better than the BEM in capturing regions of higher and lower loads across the rotor disk.

Keywords: Blade Element Momentum Method, Vortex Cylinder Model, Aerodynamic Load and Power Prediction

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Nomenclature

a	axial induction
a'	tangential induction
C_L	lift coefficient
C_D	drag coefficient
C_m	moment coefficient
C_Q	torque coefficient
C_T	thrust coefficient
$C_{T,eff}$	effective thrust coefficient
$C_{T,KJ}$	Kutta–Joukowski thrust coefficient
$C_{T,rot}$	thrust coefficient due to wake rotation
$C_{T,av}$	averaged coefficient for the radial induction function
ds/dr	Curved blade length projection correction
F	tip-loss factor
h	helical pitch
k	factor for the calculation of the elliptic integral
k_1, k_2, k_3	factors for the relationship between axial induction and thrust coefficient
k_s	normalized sectional circulation of the vortex cylinder
M	the aerodynamic moment vector
N_B	number of blades
P	aerodynamic power of the rotor
r	radius of the calculation point
R	radius of the vortex cylinder
R_{rot}	rotor radius
T	aerodynamic thrust of the rotor
U_a	axial induced velocity
U_t	tangential induced velocity
U_r	radial induced velocity
U_o	inflow wind speed
V_{rel}	relative velocity

Nomenclature

x	axial position of the calculation point with respect to the vortex cylinder
γ_b	radial bound vorticity strength
γ_l	longitudinal vorticity strength of the vortex cylinder
γ_t	tangential vorticity strength of the vortex cylinder
ρ	density of air
θ_c	cone angle
κ	dihedral angle
λ_r	speed ratio at radius r

Acronym

BEM	Blade Element Momentum Method
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
VC	Vortex Cylinder
BET	Blade Element Theory
MT	Momentum Theory
BEM-VC	Blade Element Momentum plus Vortex Cylinder
BEVC	Blade Element Theory plus Vortex Cylinder

1 Introduction

The Blade Element Momentum (BEM) method is mostly used in the wind industry and by the wind energy scientific community to simulate the aerodynamic performance of a rotor such as power, thrust, and aerodynamic stresses due to its simplicity and low computational cost but still faces challenges with accurately predicting the velocity flow fields and aerodynamic loads on wind turbines. [1][2] Additionally, in real-world applications, the BEM model may be utilized under conditions that deviate from its original assumptions, such as yawed operation or high loading. [3] However, several studies have tried to introduce corrections such as the tip-loss, sweep, and other 3D correlations to the BEM's 2D flow assumption to improve its power and thrust prediction capabilities.

Figure 1 Validation of BEM simulation against Measured C_p curve

A recent correction is the superimposition of the vortex cylinder model to the blade element theory (BET) of the BEM method, thereby replacing the momentum theory in the BEM with the VC, forming the BEVC method. [4] Findings from this recent correction show that the predicted aerodynamic characteristics are in close alignment with that of a high-fidelity lifting line (LL) method. As shown in Figure 1, the power coefficient C_p predicted by the BEM simulation is similar to actual measurement data at low wind speeds but underestimates the near peak and post peak C_p rotor performance. This is because the BEM does not correctly capture the flow characteristics around the rotor at high wind speeds and overestimates the aerodynamic losses due to tip vortices. This work describes and analyses the implementation of the vortex cylinder as a correction model to the ENERCON BEM method for improved predictions of wind turbine aerodynamic characteristics.

1.1 ENERCON

The German company ENERCON is an original equipment manufacturer (OEM) of onshore wind turbines founded in 1984 by Dr. Alloys Wobben. As a major OEM in Germany and Europe, ENERCON today provides wind turbines with capacities over 5MW and rotor blades with length over 87.5m. The ENERCON BEM method was developed to study the wind flow over the rotor blades and calculate the rotor's aerodynamic performance. [5]

Figure 2 ENERCON Onshore Wind Turbine [6]

1.2 Objective

The main objective of this work is to implement a vortex cylinder model to the existing in-house BEM method for the improvement of the aerodynamic characteristic prediction. The work targets for a detailed investigation on the possibilities and re-strictions of a cylinder vortex model on the ENERCON BEM.

The section 2 of this thesis covers detailed study on previous research work aimed at improving the aerodynamic prediction of the BEM, especially for 3D flows. Further-more, it presents detailed background knowledge on the BEM theory and the vortex cylinder (VC) theorem proposed by Joukowski [7]. In section 3, the methodology for implementing the VC model to the in-house BEM method is highlighted in detail. Finally in section 4, local rotor aerodynamic properties including axial and tangential loads, power performance and annual energy production (AEP) obtained from the BEM, BEM-VC and CFD models at various operating conditions are compared.

Figure 3 Thesis Workflow Overview

2 Literature Research

In the context of the BEM method, we directly assumed that a rotor operating at high tip speed ratio experiences a uniform 2D wind inflow and each element of the blade does not interact aerodynamically with its neighbors. Furthermore, we assume that the rotor is planar with no bending on the blades. Over the years, researchers have made efforts in modifying and correcting the BEM method for better calculation of wind turbine aerodynamic load and power. For example, Leishmann et al [14] out-lined a method for modelling unsteady aerodynamic forces on 2D airfoils. An engineering model for predicting dynamic thrust on wind turbines particularly for high-load calculations was presented by Yu et al [15]. Mann [16] focused on developing models for predicting turbulent inflows. More recently, Madsen et al [1] presented a new BEM model that accounts for unsteady induction effects and demonstrates im-proved accuracy in predicting blade loads under various operating conditions.

Some modern wind turbine designs are more flexible and there is a tendency of more prebend, larger cone angles, and larger deformations giving rise to 3D augmentation effects [17]. The tip correction is an attempt to account for the 3D effects especially at the tip vortex. Glauert corrected the BEM by applying tip loss effect based on Prandtl theory. However, Glauert's tip loss correction assumed that tip loss only affects the induced velocity but not the mass flow [18]. Wilson et al [19] corrected the mass flow as the induced velocity. However, this gave rise to some problems regarding the relationship between the induced velocity and the relative velocity, resolved by Vries et al [20]. The existing models overestimates the loading near the tip as discovered by Shen et al [21] and this led to the development of a new tip correction model for better aerodynamic prediction at the tip. Nevertheless, the BEM code widely used in de-signing most modern wind turbines does not correctly capture the influence of 3D augmentation arising from structural flexibility of the turbines. Therefore, a design based on the BEM could deviate largely from an optimal design. [25]

There has been previous work by Li et al [4] proposing a method based on the vortex cylinder model for aerodynamic load calculation of non-planar rotors. The results from this work showed that the distributed aerodynamic loads solved by the model are in good agreement with high-fidelity models.

2.1 Theoretical Background

In this section, a brief overview of the BEM-VC method is presented. The mathematical procedure for predicting the rotor power performance in this work was based on the ENERCON BEM, corrected with the vortex cylinder model (BEM-VC). In the EN-ERCON BEM, the angle of attack is determined by way of an iterative process for each blade element along the blade span incorporating local aerodynamic properties. The parameter that indicates convergence of iteration is the axial induction factor, a [30]. The axial induction factor a , indicates how much of the incoming wind is stopped by the rotor due to the exchange in momentum between the rotor and the incoming wind.

In this study, it is assumed that the rotor and its wake are contained in an elementary cylinder, the rotor has a uniform bound circulation from the blade root going out-board, there is no yaw applied to the rotor and the reduced radius due to tilt is not accounted for. The elementary vortex cylinder modeled in this work consists of the tangential vorticity, longitudinal vorticity, bound circulation and bound vorticity components, and the relationship between them is highlighted later on in the following chapter sections. The vortex model is superimposed to the BEM with the same radial distribution of bound vorticity.

The findings of this work shall be evaluated from a theoretical point of view based on the theory of the VC model referenced from literature studies. Therefore, this work includes a detailed description of the methodology in the section 3 and a verification and validation of the implemented method against the computational fluid dynamics (CFD) as a high-fidelity model and field measurements in section 4. The datasets to be used for verification and validation, respectively, were provided by the host organization as in Figure 4 and the details on how it was obtained is beyond the scope of this master thesis.

Figure 4 Comparison of local flow values of a theoretical ENERCON turbine model with public available input data provided by host organization [8]

2.2 Blade Element Momentum method

The Blade Element Momentum (BEM) method is derived from the integration of two fundamental principles: momentum theory (MT) and blade element theory (BET). This algorithm serves to assess the performance of a specific rotor design within de-fined operational parameters, including factors such as free-stream velocity (U_0), rotational speed (Ω), pitch angle (β), yaw angle, wind shear, and turbulence intensity, among others. [9]

2.2.1 Momentum Theory

In the momentum theory, it is assumed that the wind turbine is surrounded by a stream tube, and the following four positions are observed, 1, upstream of the turbine, 2, just before the turbine blade, 3, after the turbine blade, and 4 downstream of the turbine [10] as shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5 Axial Stream tube around a wind turbine [11]

As wind approaches the turbine from position 1, the turbine blades extract energy from the wind between positions 2 and 3 and this leads to a pressure drop. In this theory, it is assumed that the pressure upstream and downstream of the turbine are equal. The velocities just before the blade and right after the blade are also equal, and the wind flow between position 1 and 2, 3 and 4 are frictionless.

Between positions 2 and 3, energy is extracted from the wind and results in a pressure change. If we assumed that $P_1 = P_4$ and $V_2 = V_3$. By applying Bernoulli's equation, and after some algebra:

$$P_2 - P_3 = \frac{1}{2}\rho(V_1^2 - V_4^2) \quad (1)$$

Axial force dF_x is given by:

$$dF_x = (P_2 - P_3)dA \quad (2)$$

So that;

$$dF_x = \frac{1}{2}\rho(V_1^2 - V_4^2)dA \quad (3)$$

The axial induction a , is defined as:

$$a = \frac{V_1 - V_2}{V_1} \quad (4)$$

It can also be shown that:

$$V_2 = V_1(1 - a) \quad (5)$$

$$V_4 = V_1(1 - 2a) \quad (6)$$

Substituting the variables into equation 3 gives the axial force as:

$$dF_x = \frac{1}{2}\rho V_1^2 [4a(1 - a)] 2\pi r dr \quad (7)$$

2.2.2 Rotation Effects

Additionally in the momentum theory, it is assumed that the wind flows through/across the turbine like an annular stream tube as shown in the Figure 6.

As the wind flows from position 1 to 3, the turbine causes a rotational wake effect downstream. The downstream wake created by the blades rotates at an angular velocity ω and the blade rotates with an angular velocity Ω . Then we have that:

$$\text{Moment of Inertia } I = mr^2 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Angular Moment } L = I\omega \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Torque } T = \frac{dL}{dt} \quad (10)$$

$$T = \frac{dL}{dt} = \frac{d(mr^2\omega)}{dt} = \frac{dm}{dt} r^2 \omega \quad (11)$$

Rotating Annular Streamtube

Figure 6 Rotating Annular stream tube across a wind turbine

By differentiating and substituting the equations, we obtain:

$$T = \frac{dm}{dt} r^2 \omega \quad (12)$$

For a small element of the torque, we get:

$$dT = dm' \omega r^2 \quad (13)$$

For the rotating annular element

$$dm' = \rho A V_2 \quad (14)$$

$$dm' = \rho 2\pi r dr V_2 \quad (15)$$

$$dT = \rho 2\pi r dr V_2 \omega r^2 = \rho V_2 \omega r^2 2\pi r dr \quad (16)$$

With the angular induction factor, a' :

$$a' = \frac{\omega}{2\Omega} \quad (17)$$

Recall that $V_2 = V_1(1 - a)$ so:

Substituting the equations, we obtain the tangential force for an annular element of fluid:

$$dT = 4a'(1 - a)\rho V\Omega r^3\pi dr \quad (18)$$

2.2.3 Blade Element Theory

In the Blade Element Theory (BET), the blade is divided into N elements as shown in Figure 7 of this work. The overall performance features are computed as an integral of each element's performance along the blade span. Each blade element experiences a slightly different flow due to its different aerodynamic characteristics. From the BET, the expressions for lift C_L and drag C_D coefficients are obtained.

Figure 7 Blade splitted into elements [12]

Figure 8 Flow approaching turbine blade [11]

Figure 9 Forces experienced by the turbine blade [11]

From Figure 8, we relate the incoming velocity (V) to the turbine blade in order to deduce the relative flow onto the blades ($\tan\beta$):

$$\tan\beta = \frac{\lambda_r(1+a')}{(1-a)} \quad (19)$$

The tangential and axial forces experienced by the turbine blades are given as follows:

$$dF_\theta = dL\cos\beta - dD\sin\beta \quad (20)$$

$$dF_x = dL\sin\beta + dD\cos\beta \quad (21)$$

The lift and drag forces (dL and dD) are expressed as follows:

$$dL = C_L \frac{1}{2} \rho W^2 c dr \quad (22)$$

$$dD = C_D \frac{1}{2} \rho W^2 c dr \quad (23)$$

After substituting:

$$dF_x = N \frac{1}{2} \rho W^2 (C_L \sin\beta + C_D \cos\beta) c dr \quad (24)$$

To obtain the torque, the tangential force (F_θ) is multiplied by the blade radius r :

$$dT = N \frac{1}{2} \rho W^2 (C_L \cos \beta - C_D \sin \beta) c r dr \quad (25)$$

Where N is the number of blades and W can be deduced from Figure 8 as:

$$W = \frac{V(1-a)}{\cos \beta} \quad (26)$$

2.2.4 Tip Loss Correction

The tip loss correction comes close to modeling the 3D flow circulation around the rotor blades especially at the tip. It is implemented by introducing the Prandtl tip correction factor P, to the BEM. The correction factor ranges from 0 at the tip to 1 at the blade root and characterizes the reduction in forces along the blade.

$$P = \frac{2}{\pi} \cos^{-1} \left[\exp \left\{ - \left(\frac{\frac{B}{2 \left[1 - \frac{r}{R} \right]}}{\left(\frac{r}{R} \right) \cos \beta} \right) \right\} \right] \quad (27)$$

2.3 Kutta-Joukowski Theorem

In 1912, Joukowski introduced a simple vortex model for rotors with constant flow circulation. The model consists of helical tip vortices of strength Γ and a bound vortex of strength, $n\Gamma$ [22]. Figure 10 below shows the simple vortex model proposed by Joukowski.

Figure 10 Joukowski Rotor Model [23]

The Kutta-Joukowski theorem is a law in aerodynamics that relates the flow circulation around a body to the lift produced by the body along with the flow velocity and density. The Kutta-Joukowski theorem gives a good introduction or explanation of a rotating cylinder model, in this case the vortex cylinder model. The rotating cylinder is a combination of a stationary cylinder and vortex elementary flow. The addition of a point vortex flow leads to added circulation which leads to lift. Therefore, for a rotating cylinder, the flow is symmetric about the vertical plane, meaning that there is no drag ($C_D = 0$). However, across the horizontal plane, we have asymmetry, meaning that there is non-zero lift produced by the body. According to Kutta-Joukowski, an increase in circulation is indicative of an increase in lift. In this work, the VC theory is explained in section 2.3.

2.3.1 Kutta-Joukowski Theorem for Symmetric and Non-Symmetric Profiles

In the Kutta-Joukowski theory for symmetric profiles, lift is only generated when the angle of attack is at an angle not equal to zero. It is expressed analytically as:

$$\Gamma(r) = (C_L c(r) u_{loc})/2 \quad (28)$$

For non-symmetric profiles with cambers, the lift is generated for non-zero and zero angles of attack. The circulation for non-symmetric profiles is written as:

$$\Gamma(r) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{dC_L}{d\alpha} u_{loc} (\alpha_{eff}(r) - \alpha_0(r)) \cdot c(r) \quad (29)$$

Where; $c(r)$ is the chord radial position, u_{loc} is the local velocity, α_{eff} is the effective angle of attack, and α_0 is the cambered profile.

2.4 Vortex Cylinder (VC) Model

The vortex cylinder as in Figure 11 models a rotor's 3D flow characteristics. This model is obtained from the Kutta-Joukowski theorem. The model consists of a bound vortex disc γ_b , root vortex, and a non-expanding cylinder having longitudinal γ_l and tangential vorticity γ_t components.

Figure 11 Vortex Cylinder Model [23]

In the elementary VC model as described by Li et al [13], we assume uniform bound circulation, finite tip speed ratio, and an infinite number of blades. The assumption of an infinite number of blades is relaxed using the tip loss correction [23]. By superimposing elementary vortex cylinders, the radially varying bound circulation can be accounted for [24].

Figure 12 Superimposed elementary vortex cylinders [24]

The VC model is used in wind turbine performance analysis to determine the impact of the rotor on the velocity flow field, similar to the momentum theory in the BEM method. However, the momentum theory in the BEM method does not capture the impact of the rotor on the radial flow since the rotor is assumed flat.

As stated by Li et al [13], the tangential vorticity in the VC model contributes to the axial and radial induced velocities. The root vortex, bound vortex, and longitudinal vorticity contribute only to the tangential-induced velocity.

The BEM and VC model is linked using the relationship established by the bound circulation as in equations (29). The bound circulation is computed using the sectional aerodynamic results from the BEM such as the lift coefficient, local velocity, and angle of attack.

The bound circulation used in computing the velocity flow field of the VC rotor stems from the vortex panel method. The vortex-based panel method is often used for steady flow analysis around a body. It models the surface of an object such as an airfoil with discrete panels, each assigned a distribution of vortices called control points at the boundary layer having a circulation strength. $\Gamma = \int \Gamma_i * dS$ as shown in Figure 13.

In the vortex panel method, it is assumed that for an airfoil at a given angle of attack, the potential freestream flow is wrapped around the airfoil as a series of vortex sheets with circulation strengths that vary with the airfoil span. The total bound circulation is then computed as the integral of the sheet strength at every location.

Figure 13 Vortex Panel Method

This vortex panel method is very similar to the thin airfoil theory where the airfoil camber is made streamlined with a sheet of vorticity along the camber. However, in the vortex panel method, we now include the thickness of the airfoil.

The aim is to compute the rotor-induced velocities using the total bound circulation of each airfoil along the blade length. There is an application of boundary conditions and the so-called Kutta condition through an iterative process until convergence is reached. For an airfoil with n number of nodes, there will be $n-1$ number of panels. Through the vortex panel algorithm highlighted below, we obtain that the strength of each panel in the airfoil geometry is computed as the product of the inverse of the panel influence matrix say A , and the vector free stream flow property say B :

$$\Gamma = [A]^{-1} * \{B\} \quad (30)$$

The panel influence matrix A depends only on the blade geometry while the B vector depends on the angle of attack which is computed from the BEM. From Figure 12, we deduce that for a potential free stream inflow, the velocity at each control point will be tangent to the airfoil surface.

$$\vec{V}_{cp} \cdot \vec{n} = 0 \quad (31)$$

The velocity at each control point will be a summation of the free stream velocity and the velocity influence of panel j on the i th control point.

$$\vec{V}_{cp} = \vec{V}_{\infty} + \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \vec{V}_{jl} \quad (32)$$

The velocity influence of the panel j on the i th control point will then be proportional to the circulation strength at both ends of the panel j such that:

$$\vec{V}_{jl} = [P]_{ji} \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma_j \\ \Gamma_{j+1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

Moving forward, equation 33 is converted to a linear algebra problem such that the panel influence matrix P is enveloped in a larger matrix A where each position in A corresponds to a position in the bound circulation strength, and this results in the multiplication of the free stream velocity and the normal component of the free stream velocity.

$$\{B\} = [P]_{ji} \begin{bmatrix} \Gamma_j \\ \vdots \\ \Gamma_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (34)$$

By the vortex panel algorithm, the influence of all panels in the airfoil geometry on each control point is computed through an iterative process. Then the induced velocity at each point on the airfoil is computed as the summation of the multiplication of the free stream velocity and the angle of attack with the multiplication of the influence matrix P of all panels on each control point i and the circulation strength.

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_x \\ V_y \end{bmatrix} = V_{\infty} \begin{Bmatrix} \cos \alpha \\ \sin \alpha \end{Bmatrix} + \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} [P]_{i(x,y)} \begin{Bmatrix} \Gamma_i \\ \Gamma_{i+n} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (35)$$

The resultant velocity V_r at each point on the airfoil is obtained by:

$$V_r = \sqrt{V_x^2 + V_y^2} \quad (36)$$

The velocity for each airfoil is computed through the integration of the resultant velocity and this is applied going outboard from the blade root to the tip for axial, tangential and radial induced velocity components.

The implemented analytical models used in computing the bound circulation and the rotor-induced velocities for correcting the ENERCON BEM are highlighted in the methodology section 3. However,

the above is to explain in detail the theory behind the bound circulation which is the starting point in modelling the vortex cylinder.

Tangential Vorticity:

The tangential vorticity is simply a ratio of the total circulation of all blades (trailing vorticity strengths of all blades) to the helical pitch (distance for one complete turn of the vortex). The tangential vorticity induces the axial and radial velocities in the flow field.

Longitudinal Vorticity:

The longitudinal vorticity influences the flow rotation around the z axis giving rise to tangential flow velocity. Therefore, the circulation component associated with the longitudinal vorticity is divided by the mean of tangential velocity at both sides of the disc (due to jump in the tangential velocity when the airflow crosses the bound vortex disc).

Figure 14 Longitudinal and Tangential Vorticity component [34]

Linking Enercon BEM and VC Model:

The ds/dr term is used in correcting the aerodynamic loads predicted by the BEM by simply applying it directly to the BEM loads. We have it by the relationship below:

$$dF_N^{BEMVC} = \left(\frac{ds}{dr}\right) * dF_N^{BEM} \quad (37)$$

The lift coefficient, angle of attack, and local blade parameters are directly computed from the BEM and are utilized in computing the radial circulation.

3 Methodology

This chapter describes the requirements for modeling and implementing the vortex model to the ENERCON BEM method in the form of pseudocode as described by Li et al [13]. The possibility of superimposing the vortex cylinder model to the BEM model emanates from Branlard et al [24] work in finding the similarity between the momentum theory and the vortex cylinder model for planar and non-planar rotors.

3.1 BEM-VC Algorithm

The following implementation method is as proposed by Li et al [13].

Curved Blade Length Projection Correction:

According to Madsen et al [1], the curved blade length projection correction is the change in blade span with respect to the blade radius (ds/dr). In this work, the ds/dr is computed for three main blade configurations which are straight, static-dihedral, and dihedral-elastically deformed blades. The ds/dr value is computed mathematically as the secant of the sum of the dihedral and cone angles. The dihedral angle is computed using the rotor main axis geometry as in Figure 14.

$$\frac{ds}{dr} = \frac{1}{\cos(k+\beta)} \quad (38)$$

Where k is the local dihedral angle and β is the cone angle.

Figure 15 Rotor Coordinate System [1]

Thrust and Torque Coefficient

The thrust and torque coefficients are computed for each blade section analytically using equations 39 and 40 respectively by projecting the lift and drag concerning the rotor plane. The lift, and drag coefficients, angle of attack, and blade discretization are performed by the in-house BEM. For non-planar rotors, the radial distance between points along the blade span is not equal to the curved distance with in-plane and out-of-plane deflections [1]. To account for the inequality, we multiply the thrust and torque coefficient values obtained for each blade section by the sectional curved blade length projection correction (ds/dr).

$$C_T = \frac{dT}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U_0^2 2\pi r dr} = \frac{U_{rel}^2 C_y c N_B}{U_0^2 2\pi r} \quad (39)$$

$$C_Q = \frac{dQ}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U_0^2 2\pi r dr} = \frac{U_{rel}^2 C_x c N_B}{U_0^2 2\pi r} \quad (40)$$

Where N_B is the number of blades, U_{rel} is relative velocity, dT , and dQ are thrust and torque respectively, and U_0 is the inflow velocity.

Thrust Coefficient due to Wake Rotation:

The thrust coefficient due to wake rotation is computed using the total non-dimensional bound circulation, local speed ratio, and tangential induction factor for each blade section. Though computing the thrust coefficient due to wake rotation is optional, however, in this work, the thrust coefficient due to wake rotation is computed to ensure compatibility of the vortex cylinder model with the BEM when computing the induced velocities. [24]

$$C_{T,rot,i} = \sum_{j \geq i+1} \left(\frac{k_{s,i}}{2} \right)^2 \left(\frac{1}{\lambda^2 R_j} - \frac{1}{\lambda R_{j+1}} \right)^2 \quad (41)$$

Where;

$$k_{s,i} = \frac{\Omega \Gamma_i}{\pi U_0^2} \quad (42)$$

$$\lambda_r = \frac{\Omega r}{U_0} \quad (43)$$

$$\alpha'_i = \frac{k_{s,i}}{4\lambda_{r,i}^2} \quad (44)$$

$k_{s,i}$ is the total bound circulation, Ω Is the rotor rotational speed, U_0 Is the inflow velocity, λ Is the tip speed ratio, r is the elemental radius, Γ Is the bound circulation.

Effective Thrust Coefficient:

The effective thrust coefficient is obtained by subtracting the thrust coefficient due to wake rotation from the Kutta-Joukowski thrust coefficient. The Kutta-Joukowski thrust coefficient as seen in equation 46 relates the tangential induction factor to the total bound circulation per blade section.

Effective Thrust Coefficient:

The effective thrust coefficient is obtained by subtracting the thrust coefficient due to wake rotation from the Kutta-Joukowski thrust coefficient. The Kutta-Joukowski thrust coefficient as seen in equation 46 relates the tangential induction factor a'_i to the total bound circulation per blade section.

$$C_{T,eff,i} = C_{T,KJ,i} - C_{T,rot,i} \quad (45)$$

$$C_{T,KJ,i} = k_{s,i}(1 + a'_i) \quad (46)$$

Scaled Thrust Coefficient:

Here, the effective thrust coefficient is divided by the tip loss correction factor as in the BEM.

$$C_{T,scaled} = \frac{C_{T,eff,i}}{F} \quad (47)$$

Blade Axial Induction factor for non-planar rotor:

According to Li et al, the axial induction factor for the non-planar rotors could be equated to the blade axial induction factor as in the BEM.

$$a_B^{np} = a_{BEM}^{pl} \quad (48)$$

Figure 16 Non-planar rotor in blue with a corresponding planar rotor in red [13].

Annulus Axial Induction Factor of the Planar and Non-Planar Rotor:

According to Branlard and Gaunaa 2015a, the system closure can be determined in the form of a helical pitch $h(r)$ or the annulus axial induction factor $a(r)$ at the rotor disc as both formulations are equal. However, in this work, we use the annulus axial induction factor for computing the system closure as proposed by Li et al [13].

It is important to note that in this work, the annulus axial induction factor for a planar rotor is equal to that of the non-planar.

The system closure for the planar rotor is computed as:

$$a_i = -\frac{u_{a,i}}{U_0} = \frac{1}{2} [1 - \sqrt{1 - C_{T,eff,i}}] \quad (49)$$

However, when the effective thrust coefficient is too high (usually >1) the BEM breaks down and the vortex cylinder yields unphysical results. Therefore, we adopt a polynomial correction in equation 50 below proposed by Madsen et al 2020a [1] to account for high thrust coefficient results.

$$a_{\infty,i}^{np} = k_3 C_{T,eff,i}^3 + k_2 C_{T,eff,i}^2 + k_1 C_{T,eff,i} \quad (50)$$

Where;

$$k_3 = 0.0883, \quad k_2 = 0.0586 \quad k_1 = 0.2460$$

Tangential vorticity:

The system closure is determined at the far wake of the vortex cylinder and is used to determine the strength of the tangential vorticity. The tangential vorticity contributes to the axial and radial induced velocities.

$$\gamma_{t,i}^{pl} = \gamma_{t,i}^{np} = 2U_0 (a_{\infty,i}^{np} - a_{\infty,i-1}^{np}) \quad (51)$$

In computing the tangential vorticity, a safe handling precaution is applied by conditionally setting as zero, a baseline annulus axial induction factor of the planar rotor before the first blade section. This precaution is necessary to prevent the solver from producing unphysical results.

Tangential and Radial Induced Velocity:

The tangential and radial induced velocities are computed for each blade section as follows:

$$U_a(r, x) = \frac{\gamma_t}{2\pi} \left[\frac{(R-r+|R-r|)}{(2|R-r|)} + \frac{xk(r,x)}{2\pi\sqrt{rR}} \left(K(k^2(r,x)) + \frac{R-r}{R+r} P(k^2(r,0), k^2(r,x)) \right) \right] \quad (52)$$

$$u_t(r_i, 0) = -\frac{\Gamma_i}{4\pi r_i} (R_i < r_i < R_{i+1}) \quad (53)$$

$$U_r(r, x) = -\frac{\gamma_t}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{R}{r}} \left[\frac{2-k^2(r,x)}{k(r,x)} K(k^2(r,x)) - \frac{2}{k(r,x)} E(k^2(r,x)) \right] \quad (54)$$

$$k^2(r, x) = \frac{4rR}{(R+r)^2+x^2} \quad (55)$$

Where K and E are the complete elliptic integrals of the first and second kind respectively. The aforementioned elliptic integrals are computed from the C++ technical report, which is an extension of the C++ standard library [27]. Throughout this work, we assume a constant camber of which the exact value is proprietary data of ENER-CON. The bound circulation for a thin cambered profile is given as:

$$\Gamma(r) = \frac{1}{2} \frac{dC_L}{d\alpha} u_{loc} (\alpha_{eff}(r) - \alpha_0(r)) \cdot c(r) \quad (56)$$

3.2 Sensitivity Analysis

In this thesis, a sensitivity analysis has been performed to evaluate the effect of camber modifications on the aerodynamic performance of the blade. Camber refers to the curvature of the airfoil, and increasing the camber typically enhances the aerodynamic lift, improving the overall efficiency of the blade. However, the degree of camber must be optimized to avoid undesirable effects such as excessive drag or flow separation. In this study, three blade cambers have been analyzed, with modifications based on ENERCON's standard camber profile. The no-camber profile represents the standard airfoil with zero curvature, followed by a 1% and 2% increase from the standard camber.

Figure 18 Difference in bound circulation for all camber modifications

Figure 17 Difference in angle of attack for all camber modifications

The bound circulation was chosen as a metric to quantify aerodynamic changes induced by these camber variations. To clarify the sentence:

The absolute difference in bound circulation is calculated by directly subtracting the circulation values of the camber modifications from those of the standard camber profile, which serves as the reference, as described in the following method.

$$Bound\ Circulation_{modified} - Bound\ Circulation_{standard\ ENERCON\ camber} \quad (57)$$

Bound circulation directly correlates with the lift generated by the airfoil, making it a suitable measure of aerodynamic performance. The result in Figure 18, clearly indicates that introducing camber enhances the aerodynamic performance by increasing the bound circulation and consequently lift generation. Furthermore, aerodynamic performance is not linear with increased camber percentage. More so, increasing or decreasing the camber from the standard yields diminishing returns in the aerodynamic performance especially going outboard. Finally, the result indicates that the bound circulation depends on the camber and angle of attack.

3.3 CFD Model for Comparison

The scope of this thesis does not cover the intricate details of the results obtained from CFD simulation; however, a brief overview of the model is presented. A more detailed explanation of the CFD model is available in ref. [31, 32]

The CFD model for comparison in this work is the Menter’s Shear Stress Transport (SST) turbulence model in the Flower’s code of the German Aerospace Center (DLR). [31] Pointwise was used in generating the mesh topology. [33] Considering the nacelle and the resolved blade geometry of the wind turbine with a fully resolved boundary layer, the computation was performed for a 120° model of the wind turbine with structured grids. The structured grid enables control over the grid. To account for 3D effects, the grid was refined at the root and tip of the blade. The computation was performed on the whole flow field, with a blade tip downstream cell size of $\Delta = 0.32\text{m}$. The CFD computation was performed on a high-performance cluster having four nodes, a parallel system, and a 360-computation node located in the WRD Innovation Center of Enercon GmbH.

The blade used in the CFD simulation is of the same radius as the blade in BEM and BEM-VC computations. However, the discretization as well as the chord and relative thickness differences are shown in Figure 20 and Figure 19 and this could result in varying absolute values of the aerodynamic load.

Figure 20 Relative chord, relative radius for CFD and TPP blade models

Figure 19 Relative thickness, relative radius for CFD and TPP blade models

3.4 Test Cases

In this section, the test cases in this work are highlighted. For the uniform inflow case, there are three test cases for three different blade configurations which are straight, dihedral, and dihedral-deformed blades as seen in Figure 21. For each blade configuration, the rotor is either tilted or coned at a particular operating condition as seen from the test matrix set in Table 1 below. The blade used herein mimics the E-138 geometry including the prebend. The subsequent data of the test case can be found in the Appendix section.

Figure 21 Rotor Blade Configurations

First Test Case							
V_inf [m/s]	Ω (rpm)	Pitch [Deg]	Cone [Deg]	Tilt [Deg]	Straight	Dihedral	Deflection
8	8.30348	0	0/0/2.5	0/2.5/0	y	n	n

Table 1 Test Matrix Set

A further extension of the test cases in Table 1 above, is varying the inflow conditions in the form of veer and shear at a constant cone and tilt angle, keeping the same rotor conditions in Table 1 for all test cases. Table 2 below contains the varying inflow condition test cases.

Straight Blade						
V_inf [m/s]	Ω (rpm)	Pitch [Deg]	Cone [Deg]	Tilt [Deg]	Shear Exponent	Veer [Deg]
8	8.30348	0	2.5	0	0/0.15/0.2	0/5/8.5

Table 2 Extended Test Matrix

4 Results

In this section, the induction factors (axial and tangential), induced velocities (tangential and radial), distributed aerodynamic loads (axial and tangential), and aerodynamic power from the BEM-VC are compared with results from the BEM, CFD, and field measurement data. The motivation of this test is to determine how closely accurate the BEM-VC model predicts the influence of out-of-plane shapes on aerodynamic characteristic calculations.

4.1 Baseline straight blade with zero cones and zero tilt

The results for axial and tangential loads on the straight blade at zero cone and zero tilt simulated at a defined operating condition using the BEM, BEM-VC, and CFD models are displayed in Figure 23 and Figure 22 below. From the result, we can deduce that there is no significant difference between the load predicted by the BEM and BEM-VC. However, there is a deviation between the lower fidelity models and CFD at the root and towards the tip due to the different blade discretization as explained in section 3.2.

Figure 23 Axial load of the BEM and BEM-VC compared with CFD for straight blade zero cone, zero tilt

Figure 22 Tangential load of the BEM and BEM-VC compared with CFD for straight blade zero cone, zero tilt

4.2 Dihedral blade with zero cone and zero tilt

The steady-state simulation is performed for a static-dihedral blade using BEM and BEM-VC - models only. The curved blade length projection is used in correcting the axial and tangential load computations. From the result in Figure 24, we can deduce that there is a slight deviation in the predicted load especially closer to the blade tip. The difference is analyzed more closely in sections 4.4 to 4.6.

Figure 24 Axial load of the BEM and BEM-VC for dihedral blade with zero cone and zero tilt

Figure 25 Tangential load of the BEM and BEM-VC for dihedral blade with zero cone and zero tilt

4.3 Dihedral-deformed blade with zero cone and zero tilt

This simulation is an extension of previous work by Li et al 2022 (J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 2265 032055) which only focused on dihedral blades. Here, we extend by performing a simulation for a dihedral blade with elastic deformation. The blade deflection geometry can be seen in Figure 21.

From Figure 27, we find that the dihedral blade with elastic deformation predicts lower loads compared to the dihedral-static blade. This is due to the lesser interaction between the blade and the wind in the deformed case as compared to the dihedral blade case. The BEM load result differs very slightly from the BEM-VC result from the mid-span of the blade to the tip.

Figure 27 Axial load of the BEM and BEM-VC for deformed-dihedral blade with zero cone and zero tilt

Figure 26 Tangential load of the BEM and BEM-VC for de-formed-dihedral blade with zero cone and zero tilt

From the above plots, we can deduce that it is difficult to conclude the impact of the vortex cylinder model in the BEM from the absolute load values. Therefore, the relative difference of the absolute load predicted BEM and BEM-VC is obtained for each blade configuration by directly subtracting the load values predicted by BEM from the BEM-VC as in the equation below:

4.4 Relative Difference Zero Cone

From the result in Figure 29, we deduce that the BEM and BEM-VC models are predicting similar loads for the straight blade. For the dihedral blade, the BEM-VC model predicts a higher load compared to the BEM going outboard from the blade root. Finally, for the dihedral blade with elastic deformation, the BEM-VC predicts higher load at the blade mid-span lower loads before the blade tip, and higher values at the tip.

Figure 29 Axial load relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations zero-cone

Figure 28 Tangential load relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations zero-cone

4.5 Relative Difference Upwind Cone

To further verify the BEM-VC capacity of capture aerodynamics interactions especially for non-planar rotors, a cone of 2.5 degrees is applied to the straight, dihedral, and dihedral-deformed blade configurations. As opposed to the zero-cone case in Section 4.4, we see from the results in Coned that for the straight blade, the BEM-VC is predicting higher loads going outboard compared to the BEM, which is expected. The predicted load for the dihedral blade is similar to what was obtained for the zero-cone case, however, in order of magnitude, the load for the coned case is higher. Finally, for the dihedral blade with elastic deformation, the relative load distribution along the blade span simply follows the pattern of the deformed blade.

Figure 31 Axial load relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations Upwind Coned

Figure 30 Tangential load relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations Upwind Coned

4.6 Relative Difference Downwind Cone

The load predicted for the straight blade in the downwind cone case is identical to the predicted load for the upwind cone case. However, the dihedral and dihedral-deformed blade shows an inverse prediction of load as the upwind case.

Figure 33 Axial load relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations downwind Coned

Figure 32 Tangential load relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations downwind Coned

4.7 Relative Difference Small and Large Tilt Angle

A tilt of 2.5 degrees is applied to the rotor and from the result in Figure 34, we deduce that the rotor experiences similar loads as in the zero-cone case. The rotor is further subjected to a larger tilt angle of 7 degrees and the result in angle shows that the influence of large tilting is very small by a difference of 0.05 compared to the case with small tilt angles. Therefore, we can conclude that the BEM-VC method fails to accurately capture the effects of rotor tilting at small or large angles. This is because during tilting the entire rotor plane is affected, while the BEM-VC method primarily accounts for changes in blade geometry, such as dihedral, deflection, and cone angle.

Figure 35 Axial load relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations small Tilt

Figure 34 Axial load relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations large Tilt angle

Small Tilt Angle	
Mapping	Value
Straight blade	0
Dihedral blade	11.38
Dihedral-deformed blade	1.05
Large Tilt Angle	
Straight blade	0
Dihedral blade	11.33
Dihedral-deformed blade	1.04

Table 3 Probed Relative Axial load for small and large tilt angles

4.8 Non-Uniform Inflow – Shear and Veer

The BEM and BEM-VC model is used in running simulations of non-uniform inflow in the form of shear and veer with shear exponents of 0.15 and veer of 5 degrees for all blade configurations. The relative difference of loads predicted by most methods is displayed to determine the performance of the BEM-VC.

The straight blade configuration from Figure 33 shows no difference in load predicted by BEM and BEM-VC as expected, this is the same case as in veer. However, for the dihedral blade, the BEM-VC predicts higher loads than the BEM in the upper half of the rotor coordinate system as shown in Figure 35. Furthermore, we can deduce from Figure 36 that the BEM-VC correctly captures the effect of deflection on the rotor. For the rotor experiencing veer, we do not see any significant impact of the BEM-VC. More plots for the veer case for the straight and deformed blade configurations are shown in the Appendix section of this thesis report.

Figure 37 Relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for sheared inflow – straight blade

Figure 36 Relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for sheared inflow – dihedral blade

Figure 39 Relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for sheared inflow – deflected blade

Figure 38 Relative difference of BEM-VC and BEM for veered inflow – dihedral blade

4.9 Aerodynamic Power

In this section, the aerodynamic power from the BEM-VC and BEM models are compared relatively for each blade configuration. For this relative comparison, we use the aerodynamic power at the 8m/s inflow operating condition. The relative power difference is obtained using the formulae below:

$$\text{Straight Blade @ 8m/s: } (\text{BEM-VC}_{\text{Power}} - \text{BEM}_{\text{Power}}) / \text{BEM}_{\text{Power}}$$

Configuration	Cone 0	Cone 2.5	Tilt 2.5	Shear 0.15
Straight	0.00%	0.10%	0.00%	0.10%
Dihedral	0.13%	0.03%	0.13%	0.03%
Dihedral-deformed	0.01%	0.15%	0.01%	0.15%

Table 4 Relative Power Difference between BEM-VC and BEM for all blade configurations

Figure 40 Relative Power difference of BEM-VC and BEM

From the result above, we can see that BEM-VC power prediction diverges from the BEM's power prediction most significantly for the dihedral-deformed configuration and under certain test conditions (e.g. Cone 2.5, shear 0.15). This suggests that the BEM-VC captures additional aerodynamic effects that are not fully represented in the BEM model, particularly when accounting for blade deformation.

Further analysis may be needed to understand whether these differences lead to improved accuracy or reveal limitations in one of the models.

4.10 Verification

Comparing the predicted axial load absolute value for a straight blade with CFD shows a similar load pattern especially closer to the root. However, as expected, we do not have entirely identical results due to difference blade discretization for the CFD blade and TPP blade models as seen in Figure 41.

Figure 41 Difference of CFD and TPP blade discretization

4.11 Field Measurement Data

In this thesis work, I utilized field measurement data collected from a prototype wind turbine to validate the simulation results. The data included parameters such as wind speed, and power output measured using anemometers and a met mast. These instruments were calibrated to ensure accuracy, and data was logged over a specific period of one year, under varying operational conditions.

4.9.2 Validation

To validate our BEM-VC predicted results, we compare the normalized power performance predicted by the BEM and BEM-VC with field measurement data for four different ENERCON turbine models. From the result displayed in Figure 42, we can see that BEM-VC predicts increased power closer to

field measurement by 0.2% than the BEM for turbines 2, 3, and 4, agreeing with the predicted results from Figure 40. However, we see an opposite trend for turbine 1. This opposition in the power improvement trend is due to the inherent over-predictiveness in the turbine 1 model. Thus, in general, BEM-VC predicts power closely to field measurement better than BEM. The Cp curves of the following turbine models in comparison to field measurements are highlighted below.

Figure 42 Comparison of power performance predicted by BEM and BEM-VC against field measurement data

Figure 43 Turbine 1 Cp comparison with BEM and BEM-VC

Figure 44 Turbine 2 Cp comparison with BEM and BEM-VC

Figure 45 Turbine 3 Cp comparison with BEM and BEM-VC

Figure 46 Turbine 4 Cp comparison with BEM and BEM-VC

The radial velocity field of the dihedral and elastically deformed blade configuration and induction factors are further investigated. It can be seen in Figure 47 Axial Induction Factor from CFD, BEM, and BEM-VC with no tip loss correction that induction factors predicted by the BEM and BEM-VC are in good agreement with the high-fidelity model mostly at the mid-span region of the blade. The BEM-VC appears to predict higher induction from the root to the mid-span. This is due to the dihedral configuration of the blade used in this study. The CFD blade model is a straight blade configuration with torsion bending similar to a dihedral blade. For the BEM-VC, the blade tip, shows a spike in the axial induction factor, however, we see how this is corrected using the tip loss correction model as in Figure 47.

Figure 48 Axial Induction Factor from CFD, BEM and BEM-VC with no tip loss correction

Figure 47 Axial Induction Factor from CFD, BEM and BEM-VC with tip loss extra-distance 1.5

Figure 49 Radial flow velocity of dihedral and deformed blade compared with CFD

This plot compares the radial flow velocity across the blade span for the CFD, and BEM-VC modeling approaches. The red dashed line represents the CFD model, the green dashed line represents the BEM-VC dihedral blade and the blue dashed line represents the BEM-VC deformed dihedral blade. From the result, we can see that near the root ($r < 15\text{m}$), the CFD shows strong radial velocity peaking sharply close to the root. While the BEM-VC models predict lower radial flow compared to CFD, indicating a weaker radial transport effect in these models. At the mid-span ($r = 15\text{-}50\text{m}$), CFD shows a clear secondary peak which is not well captured by BEM-VC models and we see that the BEM-VC model underestimates the radial velocity in this region. Finally, near the tip ($r > 50\text{m}$), the radial flow velocity increases sharply for all models, peaking at the blade tip. The CFD predicts the highest radial velocity, while the BEM-VC models follow the general trend but underestimate the magnitude.

6 Conclusion and future work

In this thesis, the BEM is corrected using the vortex cylinder (VC) model. The simulation results from the BEM-VC model were compared with those of the BEM, CFD, and field measurements. As a first step, the rotor non-planarity assumption of the BEM was relaxed followed by aerodynamic simulation under uniform inflow conditions for different rotor and blade configurations. The impact of the rotor's non-planar shape in the form dihedral blade or a cone angle has been highlighted in detail. Furthermore, an extension of this work and a contribution to other research works in this area is the simulation of non-uniform inflow conditions for a blade considered to undergo elastic deformation. The results from the simulation showed that the BEM-VC and BEM predict identical results for a planar rotor. However, the BEM predicts lower loads for non-planar rotor configurations. Furthermore, the results show that BEM-VC is predicting turbine power 0.2% closer to field measurement than the BEM for turbines 2, 3, and 4. However, this significance does not hold for the turbine 1 model as in Figure 42 Due to the inherent complications with the turbine model. The discussion of these inherent complications is considered confidential and beyond the scope of this thesis.

For future work, it is beneficial to include computation of the aerodynamic forces including dynamic stall and Theordorsen effect as well as having a feedback loop for the structure to load computation to quantify correctly the integrity of the VC model to the BEM, especially for elastically deforming rotors.

In conclusion, the implemented BEM-VC model can be used for uniform and non-uniform aerodynamic simulations of large rotors having out-of-plane shapes in the form of dihedral, cone, or elastic deformation.

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APPENDIX

Second Test Case							
V _{inf} [m/s]	Ω (rpm)	Pitch [Deg]	Cone [Deg]	Tilt [Deg]	Straight	Dihedral	Deflection
8	8.30348	0	0/0/2.5	0/2.5/0	n	y	n
Third Test Case							
V _{inf} [m/s]	Ω (rpm)	Pitch [Deg]	Cone [Deg]	Tilt [Deg]	Straight	Dihedral	Deflection
8	8.30348	0	0/0/2.5	0/2.5/0	n	y	y

Table 5 Continuation of Test Matrix in Table 1

Static-Dihedral Blade						
V _{inf} [m/s]	Ω (rpm)	Pitch [Deg]	Cone [Deg]	Tilt [Deg]	Shear Exponent	Veer [Deg]
8	8.30348	0	2.5	0	0/0.15/0.2	0/5/8.5
Dihedral Elastically-Deformed Blade						
V _{inf} [m/s]	Ω (rpm)	Pitch [Deg]	Cone [Deg]	Tilt [Deg]	Shear Exponent	Veer [Deg]
8	8.30348	0	2.5	0	0/0.15/0.2	0/5/8.5

Table 6 Continuation of Extended Test Matrix in Table 2